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PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT PAIN DYSFUNCTION

Introduction

The temporomandibular joint is considered to be one of the most complex joints in terms of structure. It is a movable joint that connects the skull and the lower jaw. It is also one of the most active in the body, as it is involved in speaking, swallowing, and eating. The most prevalent diseases of this joint are characterised by the presence of pain and dysfunction. Individuals afflicted by this ailment frequently report a dull pain in the affected joint region, accompanied by symptoms such as headaches, dizziness, and discomfort in the cervical spine and the occipital region. These manifestations tend to intensify towards the late afternoon. Additionally, patients often experience auditory symptoms, including a clicking sensation in the affected joints during the act of eating, a constricted mouth opening, hearing impairment, and tinnitus. This comprehensive array of symptoms was initially documented by Kosten in 1934 and was subsequently observed in patients who had experienced the loss of all their teeth. The development of pain dysfunction can be attributed to a number of factors, including but not limited to: joint injuries, prolonged appointments with dentists without adequate rest periods, decreased bite height due to tooth loss and increased abrasion, bruxism (involuntary clenching and grinding of teeth during sleep), malocclusion, and the influence of psychological stress factors.

Keywords: *dentistry, temporomandibular joint, objective structured clinical examination, stress.*

The term "stress" is employed to denote human conditions that emerge in response to a variety of extreme influences. This phenomenon is the result of an individual's cognitive processes and their evaluation of the situation. Psychological stress is characterised by a state of anxiety for life, health and well-being. In the event of an individual being under the influence of psychological stress, it is possible that they may subconsciously or involuntarily strain various muscle groups, and in particular, the masticatory muscles. This results in the transfer of the load to the temporomandibular joint, which consequently becomes overloaded. This may later manifest itself in the form of functional disorders, particularly those affecting the temporomandibular joint.

The objective structured clinical examination (OSCE) is a component of the second part of the Unified State Qualification Examination, introduced in higher medical education institutions of Ukraine as a mandatory form of certification. This form of graduate attestation was introduced in 2019 in accordance with the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine.

The Objective Structured Clinical Examination (OSCE) is a modern type of knowledge assessment used in medicine. In this case, a student of a medical institution or a doctor who is improving his/her qualification is offered various clinical situations, observes his/her actions, analyses them and assesses his/her knowledge, ability to independently examine a patient, make a diagnosis, perform a medical procedure, provide qualified assistance, etc.

The objective structured clinical (practical) examination constitutes a fundamental component of the Unified State Qualification Examination (USQE) for students enrolled in the educational and professional programme of the second (master's) level of higher education in the specialty, specifically 221 'Dentistry' (field of knowledge 22 'Healthcare').

The purpose of the OSCE is to evaluate the demonstration of professional clinical competencies by the applicant, as a reflection of the programme learning outcomes. These outcomes can be identified and quantified in a standardised manner using a checklist.

Fundamental principles:

Objectivity - all students perform tasks of equal complexity, which are assessed using a standard tool (checklist);

Structured - students move through a certain number of stations along a certain route, where they perform tasks in the same conditions for the same period of time;

Practical (clinical) orientation - creation of situations as close as possible to clinical ones (scenarios), in which students apply the acquired theoretical knowledge and practical skills;

The examination (assessment of results) is a process that evaluates the extent to which students have acquired general and special (professional/clinical) competencies at the level of demonstration. This evaluation reflects the overall results of the educational and professional programme, which is standardised, quantified and measured for each student based on the principles specified above.

Objective. To evaluate the prerequisites for the occurrence of pain dysfunction in graduate students during the period of passing an objective structured clinical examination.

Materials and methods of the study.

In order to solve this problem, an anonymous survey was conducted among students in their fourth and fifth year of study on the dental faculty. The fourth-year students were considered a comparison group, since they did not take the OSCE, but were transferred to the next year of study based on the results of successfully completing module tests. The fourth-year students who did not achieve a pass.

The module was available for retaking for the first time, which was advantageous during the OSCE. This provision enabled graduate students who did not attain the requisite number of points during the examination to recommence their studies within the same speciality. They were permitted to resit the qualifying examination the following year, after two semesters of study. In such cases, students are permitted to retake the examination on a single occasion. Consequently, it is anticipated that the levels of anxiety and the impact of psychological stress on the body will be elevated among fifth-year students.

All students who participated in the study were administered developed questionnaires to complete during the period of preparation for module tests (4th year students) and preparation for the OSCE, and subsequently after they passed them (5th year students).

The following questions were posed to the students for discussion:

Do you feel dull, aching pain in the TMJ area?

Does the pain increase during emotional overload?

Do you notice a decrease in hearing on the corresponding side?

Do you feel congestion in the ear or noise?

Do you notice muscle twitching, in particular in the subocular area?

Do you feel stiffness in the joint at the end of the day?

Is there any teeth grinding during sleep (bruxism)?

Do you feel the presence of painful and spasmodic muscle areas?

Have you noticed any displacement of the lower jaw (S-shaped movements) during opening of the mouth?

The questionnaire also contained questions about each

student's self-assessment on the perceived stress scale, in particular:

How often in the last month did you feel nervous or stressed?

How often in the last month did you feel confident that you could cope with your personal problems?

How often in the last month did you think you could not cope with everything that you needed to do?

How often in the last month could you cope with your irritability? and other questions.

Results of the research

The analysis of the questionnaire results demonstrated that 64% of graduate students (in their fifth year of study) scored between 14 and 26 points on the perceived stress scale, indicating a moderate level of stress. Within this group, 18% of subjects reported experiencing pain in the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) during periods of emotional overload. Additionally, 18% reported twitching of the muscles in the subocular region, 18% reported pain during touch, and 18% reported a sensation of stiffness in specific muscle areas. The students in the comparison group also exhibited symptoms consistent with myofascial pain syndrome, but the proportion of students in this group who displayed such symptoms was 7%. In the context of the stress scale, it was observed that 56% of the comparison group demonstrated a score of up to 13 points, thereby indicating a low level of stress.

Conclusion.

As of the present date, the psychological well-being of the Ukrainian populace has been considerably compromised, a state of affairs that is chiefly attributable to the Russian invasion of Ukraine.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), mental health is defined as a state of well-being in which an individual is capable of realizing their potential, effectively coping with life stresses, and contributing productively to their community. It is only through mutual assistance and support in all circumstances of life that stress can be overcome.

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